

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ALEEMA ISHA bearing USN 6SU20CP001 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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College of Allied Health Sciences
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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AMRUT CHINTAN bearing USN 6SU20CP002 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms BENGIA NUNU bearing USN 6SU20CP003 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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College of Allied Health Sciences
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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms CHANDANA M P bearing USN 6SU20CP004 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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College of Allied Health Sciences
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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIDHIN P bearing USN 6SU20CP005 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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College of Allied Health Sciences
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This is to certify that Mr/Ms RESHMA RAJU bearing USN 6SU20CP006 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RIDDHI SREENIVASAN** bearing USN **6SU20CP007** has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year **2020-2021**

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College of Allied Health Sciences
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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SAKSHI bearing USN 6SU20CP008 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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College of Allied Health Sciences
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This is to certify that Mr/Ms STEPHIN GEORGY ABRAHAM bearing USN 6SU20CP009 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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